

Study of Shaft Voltage on Short Circuit Alternator with Static Frequency Converter

Authors : Arun Kumar Datta, Manisha Dubey, Shailendra Jain

Abstract : Electric machines are driven nowadays by static system popularly known as soft starter. This paper describes a thyristor based static frequency converter (or SFC) to run a large synchronous machine installed at a short circuit test laboratory. Normally a synchronous machine requires prime mover or some other driving mechanism to run. This machine doesn't need a prime mover as it operates in dual mode. In the beginning SFC starts this machine as a motor to achieve the full speed. Thereafter whenever required it can be converted to generator mode. This paper begins with the various starting methodology of synchronous machine. Detailed of SFC with different operational modes have been analysed. Shaft voltage is a very common phenomenon for the machines with static drives. Various causes of shaft voltages in perspective with this machine are the main attraction of this paper.

Keywords : capacitive coupling, electric discharge machining, inductive coupling, shaft voltage, static frequency converter.

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